

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF PEEL FAILURE BETWEEN ALUMINA CERAMICS AND GLASS FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

Tom Thorvaldsen¹, Bernt B. Johnsen¹, Tyler P. Jones^{1,2}, Dennis B. Rahbek¹ and
Luiz F. Kawashita³

¹Norwegian Defence Research Establishment (FFI)
P.O. Box 25, Instituttveien 20, NO-2027 Kjeller, Norway
Email: tom.thorvaldsen@ffi.no, bernt.johnsen@ffi.no,
tyler.jones@ffi.no, dennis-bo.rahbek@ffi.no, web page: <http://www.ffi.no>

²US Air Force Office of Scientific Research
Arlington, United States
Email: tyler.jones@ffi.no, web page: <http://www.wpafb.af.mil/afri/afost/>

³Advanced Composites Centre for Innovation and Science, University of Bristol
Bristol BS8 1TR, United Kingdom
Email: luiz.kawashita@bristol.ac.uk, web page: <http://www.bris.ac.uk>

Keywords: Composites, Ceramics, Cohesive zone modelling, Fracture energy, Peel testing

ABSTRACT

In this work, experimental techniques, analytical calculations and finite element modelling (FEM) have been employed to investigate the failure between an alumina ceramic and a glass fibre-reinforced polyester composite under quasi-static loading in peel.

Peel strength was determined experimentally employing the fixed arm peel test. In this test, the flexible glass fibre/polyester peel arm was peeled off the rigid ceramic substrate at a peel angle of 45 degrees. Different surface treatments of the alumina resulted in different levels of adhesion between the ceramic and the composite, and several cases have been included in the analysis of the fracture energy. At low levels of adhesion, the analytical models gave a good estimate of the fracture energy. However, at higher levels of adhesion the composite material showed clear signs of in-plane compressive and tensile damage due to the severity of the bending deformation, and the analytical solutions were no longer valid.

FEM analyses were performed in MSC.Marc/Mentat, where built-in tools for cohesive zone modelling (CZM) were used to model the fracture of the composite-ceramic interface. The constitutive model of the cohesive elements was expressed as a bilinear function of the traction versus the effective opening displacement. The glass fibre-reinforced polyester composite was modelled employing composite elements, whereas the alumina ceramic was modelled using 3D brick elements. The FEM analyses were found to give a very good estimate of the fracture energy by reproducing accurately the dissipative nature of the composite material for the peel test.

1 INTRODUCTION

A number of different quasi-static test methods may be used to evaluate the adhesion in adhesively bonded joints. One of the factors that influence the choice of test method is whether the adhesive joint is made of rigid-rigid, rigid-flexible or flexible-flexible adherends. The peel test is a commonly used test for assessing the failure of adhesive joints where at least one of the adherends is flexible [1;2]. The peeling is usually conducted at a certain rate and at a certain peel angle. Different test configurations may be employed, but the basic principle is relatively similar for the different peel tests, in that the

average peel force per unit width of a rectangular specimen, i.e. the peel strength, is determined. Further analysis of the test data can also provide the adhesive fracture energy of the adhesive bond.

In the present work, the fixed arm peel test was used to experimentally evaluate the adhesion between a relatively flexible glass fibre-reinforced polymer composite and a rigid alumina ceramic. The peel angle was maintained constant at 45 degrees by allowing the rigid substrate, which was attached to a jig, to move along a linear bearing system during the pulling of the composite peel arm. The matrix of the composite consisted of a thermoplastic polymer, and a heat-vacuum technique was employed to bond the composite to the alumina. The alumina was subjected to different surface treatments to vary the adhesion to the composite material. Peel strengths and adhesive fracture energies were calculated.

For additional understanding of the investigated adhesive system, finite element modelling (FEM) was also undertaken. Different fracture mechanics approaches for estimating the stiffness and strength of an adhesive joint are implemented in commercial software packages, such as the Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT) and the J-integral. However, these methodologies have some drawbacks that limit their use and applicability [3]. An alternative method is cohesive zone modelling (CZM), which is considered as a promising approach. In many cases, the CZM method avoids the restrictions of the other methods, and for that reason it was employed here.

2 EXPERIMENTAL TESTING

2.1 Materials and surface treatments

The alumina ceramic (aluminium oxide, Al_2O_3) Alotec 98 SB from CeramTec (Plochingen, Germany) was employed. The alumina content was 98%, density 3.8 g/cm^3 , porosity $< 2\%$, medium grain size $6 \mu\text{m}$, Vickers hardness 13.5 GPa, and Young's modulus 335 GPa. The tile size was $150 \text{ mm} \times 150 \text{ mm} \times 10 \text{ mm}$.

The composite consisted of glass fibres in a thermoplastic polyester (low-melting-temperature polyethylene terephthalate, LPET) matrix, delivered by Comfil (Gjern, Denmark). A woven fabric of glass and LPET fibres (balanced twill 2/2) was employed. The consolidated composite material has fibre content 57% by weight and 42% by volume, and density 1.87 g/cm^3 .

The alumina tiles were subjected to different surface treatments prior to preparation of specimens for mechanical testing. The surface treatments are described in Table 1. The FPL etch is traditionally used on aluminium in the aerospace industry and was included as a benchmark reference.

Table 1: Alumina surface treatments.

Surface treatment	Procedure
As-received	n/a
Degreased	acetone degrease
FPL etched	acetone degrease; etching in two parts sodium dichromate, ten parts sulphuric acid and 30 parts water; 10 min at $55\text{-}60^\circ\text{C}$
Silane treated	acetone degrease; silane treatment in 1 wt.% γ -glycidylxypropyltrimethoxysilane (GPS); one hour hydrolysis in pH 5 water; 10 min immersion; 60 min drying at 93°C

2.2 Preparation of test specimens

Rectangular alumina/composite specimens were prepared for peel testing. Five layers of the woven glass fibre/LPET fabric were first placed on the surface-treated alumina tile. On one side, the fabric was extended beyond the edge of the alumina tile to form the material for a peel arm. A fluoropolymer film was placed along the same edge, between the alumina and the fabric, to act as a starter crack during the peel testing. The alumina/fabric assembly was then heated to 215°C for 75 min under vacuum. The high temperature resulted in melting of the thermoplastic LPET fibres, which then filled the free space between the glass fibres. Upon cooling, the thermoplastic consolidated, resulting in a

composite with a continuous LPET matrix. As a result of the production process (no adhesive was applied), the LPET matrix provided the adhesion between the alumina and the composite. Finally, test specimens were cut from the alumina/composite panel. An illustration of the peel test specimen, with the dimensions indicated, is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Peel test specimen with the dimensions indicated (after testing).

2.3 Peel testing

The fixed arm peel test was used to evaluate the adhesion between the surface treated alumina and the consolidated composite material [2], see Figure 2. The testing was performed using a Zwick BZ 2.5/TN1S testing machine together with an angled specimen holder attached to a table on a linear bearing system. The peel angle was set to 45 degrees. This experimental set-up allowed the specimen to slide sideways when the composite peel arm was gripped. A controlled displacement was applied to the end of the composite arm. The crosshead speed of the test machine was set to 2.93 mm/min, which resulted in an average crack growth rate of the propagating crack of 10.0 mm/min. During the tests, force versus displacement curves were recorded, and these curves were then used to evaluate the peel strength of the specimen. The force was set to zero prior to gripping the peel arm.

Around 120 mm of peel fracture could usually be established for each alumina surface. The regions close to the starter film and the end of the specimen were, however, not taken into account when analysing the results. This resulted in around 70 mm of peel fracture in the 45 degree set-up being analysed. The average peel strength was obtained by dividing the average force in the analysed region with the average specimen width in the same region. A minimum of five specimens for each surface treatment were tested.

2.4 Calculation of the fracture energy

The adhesive fracture energy was calculated using the Excel spreadsheet 'IC Peel' developed by Imperial College London, UK [2]. 'IC Peel' is freely downloadable from the Imperial College website [4]. The calculations in the spreadsheet take into account the different contributions to the fracture energy, that is, the stored strain energy in the peeling arm, the energy dissipated during tensile deformation of the peeling arm, as well as the energy dissipated due to the plastic bending of the peel arm [1].

The 'IC Peel' spreadsheet calculations require the elastic-plastic tangent stiffness of the peeling arm material. Tensile tests were therefore performed to obtain stress-strain curves of the same composite material as that used in the peel test specimens. No yield point was observed prior to fracture. The adhesive fracture energy was then calculated analytically in the 'IC Peel' spreadsheet employing the bilinear elastic-plastic fit. A detailed explanation of the method is given in the ESIS TC4 test protocol by Moore and Williams [2].

Figure 2: Fixed arm peel test at 45°. (a) From the initial test phase, and (b) detail from the crack tip region.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The three alumina surface treatments resulted in an increase in the alumina/composite adhesion, compared to the as-received surface. These results were presented by Lausund *et al.* [5], and the peel strength values are reproduced in Table 2. Several comments can be made about this observation. Firstly, the following increasing order of alumina/LPET adhesion was observed: as-received < acetone degreased < FPL etched < silane treated. Secondly, there was a trend of increasingly unstable crack propagation with increasing adhesion, as illustrated by the peel curves shown in Figure 3. In cases with relatively low adhesion, e.g. the as-received alumina, the crack usually propagated in a stable manner. However, as the adhesion increased, more unstable crack growth was observed. This can be seen particularly for the silane treated surface, resulting in the so-called ‘stick-slip’ behaviour. The result is a large difference between the highest and lowest measured forces during the peel test. Thirdly, there was a trend of a shift in the locus of failure with increasing adhesion. At relatively low adhesion, the failure was mainly in the alumina/LPET interface, although some cohesive failure in the LPET matrix was observed, while at higher adhesion the failure was predominantly ‘cohesive’ through the composite material. For the silane treated surface, the failure was exclusively cohesive.

At relatively low adhesion, the ‘inelastic’ (i.e. nonlinear irreversible) deformation of the composite peel arm was negligible. However, with increasing adhesion more and more inelastic deformation was observed. This was a direct consequence of micro-cracking of the composite material. The micro-cracking was clearly visible on the composite surface, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Table 2: Calculated peel strength and fracture energy values.

Surface treatment	Peel strength [N/mm]	Fracture energy, IC Peel [J/m ²]
As-received	9.6 ± 0.6	2810 ± 140
Degreased	13.8 ± 0.9	4050 ± 270
FPL etched	15.7 ± 0.9	4610 ± 260
Silane treated	19.9 ± 2.3	5830 ± 680

Figure 3: Example peel curves for the different alumina surfaces: (a) as-received, (b) degreased, (c) FPL etched, and (d) silane treated. Measured force versus crosshead displacement in the 45 degree peel test set-up is displayed.

Figure 4: Micro-cracking of the composite peel arm.

4 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

Micro-cracking in the peel arm results in inelastic deformation. Inelastic deformation due to micro-cracking of fibre composites is not fully accounted for in the ‘IC Peel’ tools. Moreover, the ‘IC Peel’ tools generally require an adhesive with a finite thickness ($h_a > 0$ in ‘IC Peel’ terminology), which is not the case for the test specimens considered in our case. A FEM model study was therefore undertaken for increased accuracy of the measured fracture energy, and for improved understanding of this peel test. Only the case with the lowest adhesion, i.e. the as-received alumina, has been investigated and included in this paper.

The software MSC.Marc/Mentat 2013.1 was applied for the simulations. Using the implemented features for cohesive zone modelling (CZM) [6], it was possible to define a zero thickness for the adhesive, as well as to take into account geometric and material non-linear behaviour. As part of analysis, the deactivation properties of the cohesive elements after damage (i.e. at damage $D = 1$) was also altered.

4.1 Model set-up

The composite was modelled using Marc element type 149, which is a 3D eight-node composite brick element. One composite element with four plies was used in the thickness direction. Each ply was modelled using an orthotropic material model, with material parameters for a woven glass fibre/polymer material. The material parameters are given in Table 3. The alumina was modelled using Marc element type 7, which is a 3D eight-node brick element. An isotropic material model was assumed for the alumina ceramic, with much higher elastic stiffness compared to the composite. The material parameters are given in Table 4.

The interface between the composite and the ceramic was modelled using Marc element 188, which is a 3D eight-node interface element, with zero thickness. The constitutive model of the cohesive elements was expressed as a bilinear function of the traction versus the effective opening displacement, assuming a mixed-mode situation, due to the peel angle of 45 degrees. The parameters are given in Table 5. The parameter value for the cohesive energy (G_C) was in our simulations obtained from the calculated value using the ‘IC Peel’ tools for the as-received test specimens, as described in Section 2.4 and Section 3, and given in Table 2. The other parameters of the traction-separation constitutive model were based on experience from other test cases, as well as trial and error to make a best fit with the experimental tests for the case of adhesive failure.

The interaction between the different parts of the model, i.e. the composite, the ceramic and the interphase, was defined through a contact table.

Table 3: Material properties for each (orthotropic) ply of the composite.

Engineering constant	Description		Value
E_1	Young’s modulus	[GPa]	20.2
E_2	Young’s modulus	[GPa]	20.2
E_3	Young’s modulus	[GPa]	4.65
ν_{12}	Poisson’s ratio	–	0.3
ν_{23}	Poisson’s ratio	–	0.3
ν_{31}	Poisson’s ratio	–	0.068
G_{12}	Shear modulus	[GPa]	3.0
G_{23}	Shear modulus	[GPa]	2.0
G_{31}	Shear modulus	[GPa]	3.0

Table 4: Material properties for the isotropic alumina ceramic.

Engineering constant	Description		Value
E	Young’s modulus	[GPa]	335
ν	Poisson’s ratio	–	0.21

Table 5: Parameters for bilinear traction-separation constitutive relation for the cohesive elements.

Engineering constant	Description		Value
G_C	Cohesive energy	[kJ/m ²]	2.8
ν_C	Critical opening displacement	[mm]	0.01
ν_m	Maximum opening displacement	[mm]	0.056
β_1	Shear-normal stress ratio	–	1.2
β_2	Shear-normal cohesive energy ratio	–	1.0

The quasi-static numerical simulation of the peel test described above was divided into two phases: 1) the bend phase and 2) the peel phase. The geometry was initially (at quasi-time zero) oriented in a

vertical position (in the global coordinate system). Different boundary conditions and loads (in the form of displacement controlled movement) were applied at different locations, as indicated in Figure 5, for each phase. Note that a full 3D simulation was conducted; the model is displayed in the xz-plane for clarity.

Figure 5: Initial geometry and orientation of the test specimen geometric model. 'A', 'B' and 'C' indicate the locations of the nodes where boundary conditions are applied. The 3D model is displayed in the xz-plane for clarity.

In the bend phase, the model specimen was rotated to include the bending and forces introduced from mounting the test specimen into the test fixture, where the composite peel arm was fixed in the fixture grip. After rotation, the ceramic made an angle of 45 degrees with the horizontal axis. During this bend phase, the rightmost bottom corner nodes of the ceramic (location 'A' in Figure 5) were free to rotate about the y-axis, whereas the rightmost upper corner nodes (location 'B') were moved according to the path of a 45 degrees rotation. Moreover, the upper part of the composite peel arm (location 'C') was restricted from rotation about the y-axis, but free to move in the x and z directions. The crack length was increased due to the bending.

In the peel phase, the composite peel arm being gripped (at location 'C') was pulled in the global x direction using displacement control, with the result that the composite was peeled off the ceramic tile. The rightmost bottom corner nodes of the ceramic (location 'A') were now free to move in the global z direction, to mimic the free sliding motion of the test rig in the experiment. The horizontal displacement was dependent on the crack opening and the bending moment in the composite peel arm.

4.2 Model results

The deformed test specimen showing the crack length at the end of each of the two defined phases is shown in Figure 6 for two different cases: 1) the deactivation option for the cohesive elements was set to 'on', and 2) the deactivation option for the cohesive elements was set to 'off'. Turning the deactivation option 'on' means that fully damaged cohesive elements will not partake in further analysis, but are left in the post file, whereas if not deactivated, the elements will partake in the analysis despite their damage level.

Figures 6a and 6b show the deformed specimen at the end of each phase for the case where the deactivation of the cohesive elements is set to 'on' (deactivated). Figures 6c and 6d show the deformed specimen at the end of each phase for the case, where the deactivation of the cohesive elements is set to 'off' (non-deactivated). For all subfigures, the colour bar indicates the level of damage of the

cohesive elements (from 0 for pristine to 1 for failed elements). Note again that a full 3D simulation was run in each case, but for clarity only the xz-planes are displayed here. As can be observed from the figures, the crack length, as well as the levels of damage in the cohesive elements, is slightly larger for the case of deactivation of the cohesive elements. In both cases, the crack opening, the crack length and the bending of the composite peel arm are in accordance with the experimental results.

Figure 6: Undeformed and deformed test specimen at the end of each phase. (a) and (b) show the case where the deactivation option for the cohesive elements is set to ‘on’ (deactivated), whereas (c) and (d) show the case where the deactivation option is set to ‘off’ (non-deactivated).

To further analyse the difference between the calculated results for the two cases of deactivated and non-deactivated cohesive elements, respectively, as well as comparing with the experimental data, the tension force in the composite peel arm as a function of vertical displacement was considered. The curves are displayed in Figure 7. The blue curve shows the experimental data for one of the as-received test specimens, the red curve displays the calculated data in case of deactivating the cohesive elements, and the green curve shows the calculated data in case of not deactivating the cohesive elements. The force measured experimentally had a higher peak in the first part of the test. This is related to the starter crack created by the film insert, and the test data in this region are therefore not included. Thus, we restrict the analysis to the vertical deformation range from 10 to 30 mm.

For the analysed region both simulation cases agree well with the experimental data. The calculated averaged peel strength is found to be close to the experimental values, as given in Table 6. The deactivation modelling case results in a larger variation of the calculated force (and the peel strength), with the same force range as for the experimental data.

Figure 7: Tension force as a function of vertical (crosshead) displacement of the composite arm.

Table 6: Average peel strength from five of the as-received test specimens and the simulations.

Test case	Peel strength [N/mm]
Experimental, as-received	9.57
FEM, deactivated CZM elements	9.84
FEM, non-deactivated CZM elements	9.46

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, experimental techniques, analytical calculations and finite element modelling (FEM) were employed to estimate the quasi-static failure in peel between an alumina ceramic and a glass fibre-reinforced polyester composite.

From the experimental tests and calculations using the 'IC Peel' spreadsheet, the fracture energy was found to vary in the range 2800–5800 J/m² for test specimens with different surface states of the alumina. In general, the as-received specimens had the lowest fracture energy, while the surface treatments resulted in higher fracture energies.

The case with the lowest surface energy that was measured experimentally, i.e. the as-received alumina, was investigated by FEM. Two different simulations were run for a relevant set of material parameters for the composite and the ceramic. The parameters for the bilinear traction-displacement constitutive relation for the interphase were selected to fit with the experimental data. The deactivation option of the cohesive elements was set to 'on' or 'off' in the two test cases.

The FEM calculations were found to agree well with the experimental data. In both cases, the crack opening, the crack length and the bending of the composite peel arm were in accordance with the experimental results. This indicates that the chosen set of values was representative for modelling the current peel test.

Future work should include modelling of test specimens with higher experimentally measured fracture energy values. The main aim of the modelling should be to determine the adhesive fracture energy when inelastic deformation of the peel arm is occurring. This inelastic deformation is not accounted for in the 'IC Peel' spreadsheet. Furthermore, since the CZM method is known to be very

mesh sensitive, a more thorough study should also include mesh refinement, and the influence of mesh size on fracture energy, crack length and bending of the composite peel arm.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank Kristian B. Lausund for conducting the peel testing and Bård R. Karlsten for giving valuable input to the modelling.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. J. Kinloch, C. C. Lau, and J. G. Williams, "The peeling of flexible laminates", *International Journal of Fracture*, **66**, 1994, pp. 45-70.
- [2] D. R. Moore and J. G. Williams, "A protocol for the determination of the adhesive fracture toughness of flexible laminates by peel testing: Fixed arm and T-peel methods", London, United Kingdom: Mechanical Engineering Department, Imperial College London, 2010.
- [3] D. Álvarez, B. R. K. Blackman, F. J. Guild, and A. J. Kinloch, "Mode I fracture in adhesively-bonded joints: A mesh-size independent modelling approach using cohesive elements", *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, **115**, 2014, pp. 73-95.
- [4] Imperial College London website; <http://www3.imperial.ac.uk/meadhesion/testprotocols/peel>, 2015.
- [5] K. B. Lausund, B. B. Johnsen, D. B. Rahbek, and F. K. Hansen, "Surface treatment of alumina ceramic for improved adhesion to a glass fibre-reinforced polyester composite", *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, in press, 2015.
- [6] MSC Software; www.mscsoftware.com, 2015.